

Technological drive from past to future?

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Conquering the Land: Nazi Germany's Railways in the Far North

The Nordic countries are characterized by a rather difficult geography when it comes to construction of infrastructure, and which has made travelling and transportations rather challenging, particularly in the northernmost areas. During the Second World War, these areas were of particular interest to Nazi Germany, mainly for strategic reasons, but insufficient infrastructure made the movement of troops and supplies difficult. When Germany gained control over occupied Norway and access to allied Finland in the early 1940s, a priority was therefore to develop the infrastructure in the north, focusing mainly on railways. The project of extending the railway network in Norway progressed slowly and steadily over the war years, under the supervision of the Wehrmacht and engineers from Organisation Todt.

In Finland, the German plan was to build a more than 500 km long field railway parallel to the Jäämerentie, the only road connecting the "capital" of northern Finland to its northernmost outpost Petsamo, which was incorporated in the young republic in the early 1920s. The Finns had actually considered the possibilities of constructing this railway before the war, but abandoned the plan due to the difficult geography, and soon enough the Germans were forced to do the same. However, the dream of building this railway lingered in the mind of a German engineer, the head of Organisation Todt in Finland. I would argue that the idea of the railway was, besides being a part of the German war machine, to conquer the hostile landscape which caused so much trouble for the German troops and to display the superiority of German engineers. Furthermore, Hitler emphasized that the railway was going to be built by exploiting the labor of 10.000 Soviet prisoners of war, highlighting the human costs of infrastructure construction, that also served as a way of defeating the enemy.

LUNDIN Per

Confronting Class: The American Motel in Early Post-war Sweden

In Swedish tourism discourse, the car-centered American way of life was by the mid-1950s met with enthusiasm. In the case of accommodation, it was above all the motel that served to symbolize the positive values associated with the American model of modernity. The great expectations placed on the motel did not materialize as anticipated, however. In fact, already by the early 1960s, the motel had been brought into disrepute, and it would remain a marginal phenomenon in Swedish auto tourism. This paper singles out class as one of the decisive factors for this change of events. The tourism discourse was dominated by the bourgeois middle classes, and only a few of the Swedish motels were built to meet their expectations. The majority offered instead basic lodging for truck drivers, an occupational group embodying a working-class culture that many placed at the very bottom of the social hierarchy. The motel thus materialized in two entirely different cultural and social settings, and it developed into an arena for cultural class-related confrontations. Middle-class dreams collided with blue-collar realities, and in this clash, the discontent latent in great expectations became manifest.

LYTVYNKO Alla

Science and Technology History Studies in the National Academy of Science of Ukraine

The Ukrainian Academy of Sciences was founded on November 14, 1918. In the spring of 1928, academician I. Malinovsky proposed to organize a Commission on the history of knowledge at the Academy. The Commission for the History of Natural Sciences was established on February 13, 1934, and existed until 1942. In 1946, a Department for the history of mathematics (headed by Y.Shtokalo) was established at the Institute of Mathematics. In December 1948 academician V.Danilevsky proposed to create the Institute of the History of Engineering to study the history of national engineering

and technical sciences, technical education, technical literature, technical terminology. On March 11, 1949 the Department for the history of technology at the Institute of Heat Power Engineering, as well as the Commission for the History of Technology (headed V.Danilevsky) were organized. It was planned to transform the Commission into the Institute for the History of Technology, but due to lack of funds, the intention was not realized.

On January 4, 1963, on the basis of the Department for the history of mathematics and the Department for the history of technology The Sector for the History of Natural Science and Technology (originally called The Sector for the History of Technology and Natural Science) was organized.

In 1986, based on the Sector and the science divisions of the Council for the Study of the Productive Forces of Ukraine the Center (now Institute) for Scientific and technological potential and science history studies was organized (headed G.Dobrov). In this center, the Department of the history of science and technology was established (now called the Department of the history and sociology of science and technology).

MAAT Harro

Temperate and Tropical Rice across the Atlantic: How the Americas became a Breeding Site for Asian and African Rice Farmers

The historian and geographer Judith Carney labelled the small plots where African slaves were allowed to grow their own food "the botanical gardens of the dispossessed." By growing crops and medical plants they had brought with them, enslaved Africans maintained some of their cultural identity, creating social confirmation and mental support in surviving the harsh conditions. In this paper, it is shown that these plots were also testing grounds, making the Africans not only conservationist but innovators too. The focus of this paper is on rice, a crop with many varieties, grouped according to morphological features and the major geo-climatic zones where they grow. Because Africans ended up in a variety of climatic zones in South, Central and North America, when they engaged in rice farming they selected varieties fit for the specific

environments their farm was located in. Specific attention is given to Suriname and British Guiana after the abolition of slavery. British and Dutch colonial experts got an interest in the rice farms of the ex-slaves as well as from the ex-indentured laborers from Asia. Several of the varieties grown by these farmers were introduced back to rice farmers in Africa and Asia. The emerging rice farms in the Americas thus became an important source for improvement of the rice crop across the world. The paper follows some of the specific rice varieties in their travels and how they became icons for globalization at the one hand, and adjustment to specific geo-climatic zones on the other.

MACLENNAN Anne

Radio, Home, and Country: The Listener, the Medium, and the Network, 1922-1960

Radio entered the Canadian home, rapidly however, there were a variety of obstacles to overcome through manufacturing changes, audience expectations, and network expansion. The domestication of radio initially meant the device had to be made suitable for the home. Its appearance and function was altered. The early radio operators returned from the First World War ready to bring radio to their communities, but were met with some resistance. Listeners did not understand how the sounds and music could enter their home without the assistance of wires. Like phantoms and ghosts the entry of broadcasting into the home had to be explained and as the technology evolved, it became more palatable to the audience. This paper depends on interviews with surviving members of the radio audience during the 1930s, radio import and purchase data, newspapers, and archival research including the advertisements. The early Canadian and American radio manufacturers adapted their designs not only with respect to the early fears, fit in the home, but also technical improvements. Equally important to overcoming the fears and manufacturing challenges was the network itself. The national network finally blanketed most of the country in time for the Royal Tour of 1939, but conveniently prior to the Second World War, when radio became a crucial tool for